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Role of listening comprehension in teaching process of A2 level learners

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to demonstrate role of listening comprehension in teaching process of A2 level learners. Consequently, it considers new selected pedagogical interactive technologies and experimental suggestions to develop one of the perceptive skills for young learners at secondary schools. One of the essential contemporary educational issues in the field of foreign language acquisition is enhancing listening comprehension skills. Acquiring the effective ways of teaching listening can lead to considerable improvements in language pedagogy to teacher's advantage. The primary aim of the paper is to discuss the practical and methodological usefulness of the concept of the perception base of the language. It also highlights the role of structural features and frequency of linguistic units in helping to identify teaching priorities in English language teaching while working with A2 level learners, especially, for training listening skills.

Key words: Summarization, facilitate, interaction, intrinsic, extrinsic inferencing, motivation, self-confidence, foster, barriers receptive, elaboration, imagery, motivation

1 Introduction

It is obvious that the government of Uzbekistan always shows a great desire to educate the youth foreign languages to help them get good prospects for promotion in the world. Therefore, our present president SH. M. Mirziyoyev is trying to create new opportunities for youngsters to study abroad to develop their proficiency in foreign languages.

The impact of the new curriculum and EFL reform in Uzbekistan was huge on pre-service and in-service teacher training, materials design and teachers' continuing professional development areas. The new standard required the whole system of foreign languages teaching to rethink and reform the approaches used in educational institutions.

Listening skills play a significant role in dealing with any language and the English language is also not exception from this. As far as the researcher is concerned, to master this skill a learner needs some outer and/or inner effect or encouragement. And automatically this issue is related to comprehension. It goes without saying that when an applicant becomes a student, a great demand of focusing on language skills comes into being in front of the class. The researcher is going to hold an investigation about how to comprehend junior pupils to develop their listening skills. It has been continually disputing that learner's motivation helps to take in knowledge effectively and the ways leading to this mount has been sought, found and analyzed. Motivation gives a great inspiration in a particular action of a learner. This potency may cause several efficient consequences, for example, self-confidence of a learner is raised, intention to learn more and discover unknown sides of abilities is increased, positive opinions are appeared in the mind of a learner.

Regarding motivation, the main findings of this study indicate that student choices and learner autonomy are significant for enhancing student motivation. Also, the findings suggest that the use of student questions to promote communication from diverse perspectives is a significant motivational tool. The researcher observed lessons of some groups of freshmen pupils. An interest has born to take a research about listening skills and has chosen the relevance between motivation and listening skills in obtaining and developing fluent English. Nowadays the English language is paid attention very seriously. As it contains 4 main skills, listening is also one undeniable of them. The result which is going to be expected is raised knowledge and changed attention of learners towards

listening perception. Participants' listening comprehension of motivation is going to be measured by English motivation comprehension.

2 Materials and method

A) Effectiveness of receptive skill

Listening is a skill that underlies rest of the necessary skills. It is the key to developing and maintaining relationships, making decisions and solving the problems. People spend as much as half of their communication time for listening. The importance of listening comprehension in L2 learning is now recognized very well. Researchers and textbook designers are more and more aware of its growing importance; they not only recommend that listening should be taught in L2 learning programs but insist that adequate materials and strategies should be used to teach it efficiently. Consequently, listening skills need to be encouraged and, most importantly, pupils must be shown the appropriate strategies when they are exposed to different listening materials. Listening involves hearing the speakers words, understanding the message and its importance to the speaker, and communicating that understanding to the speaker. The apparent problem is that among all the communication skills, listening is the earliest learned and the most frequently used, yet it seems to be the least mastered.

Listening is an essential and undervalued skill, notes. Why is it then that while the skill of listening is identified by many researchers as one of the most important qualities people can possess, poor listening is identified repeatedly as the most common deficiency? Unfortunately, listening skills are very often ignored or just taken for granted [1].

According to Hlaviso Albert Motlhaka, professor of Indiana University of Pennsylvania School of Graduate Studies and Research Department of English, listening skills are an essential aspect of the development of motivation which empowers pupils to develop their communication and critical thinking skills necessary for functioning competently in the ESL classroom.

It is quite clear that interactive listening is imperative in our daily life as we share ideas because we spend more time listening to one another in order to respond appropriately in an overall language learning as compared to other learning skills [2]. In the ESL classroom, it is easy to see that interactive listening plays a significant role in enhancing ESL pupils' comprehensible input and advancement of ESL learning when teachers create lesson plans that encourage pupils to connect the content to their own lives through listening because they are then able to learn on their own. For these reasons, this research contributes to a better understanding of the perceived ESL pupils' motivation and the strategies used by ESL teachers.

Besides that the development of active listening is essential to pupils' ability to negotiate language outside of the classroom. Given the relevance of this statement, it is clear that successful ESL interaction either between school teachers and learners, parents and children, medical personnel and patients or law enforcement officials and suspects, is primarily dependent on effective interactive listening skills.

Also learners in an interactive listening classroom have good learning opportunities to make it work, not merely to make it right, while negotiating meanings in interactive listening tasks. For example, teachers can give pupils contextualized listening activities in which pupils identify supporting details, which boost their listening ability and confidence to learn ESL. Therefore, motivation may come from the individual learner's emotional satisfaction or pleasure to make learning enjoyable through compelling interaction.

Cohen (1988) suggested that teachers should design a series of stimulating discussion activities that encourage pupils to express their points of view on a given topic, which advances pupils' comprehensible input and lets the class generate goals to be accomplished. To illustrate, teachers can demonstrate to pupils the benefits of what is taught in an ESL classroom by encouraging pupils to respect each other's viewpoints while praising pupils for attentively listening to one another.

Thus, what emerges from this discussion of motivation is the underlying theme of this research in which ESL pupils' desires and goals are generally related to their motivation and success to learn the foreign language and its culture. Finally, the discussion of intrinsic, instrumental motivation reveals that having a specific goal in ESL learning helps pupils focus their efforts and maintain their motivation.

In fact, several researchers have contended that listening skills are regarded by employers as a major requirement for employment of job seekers, as well as a significant skill for promotions (Brownell, 1993; Brownell & Janusik, 2002, as cited in Thompson et al., 2004; DiSalvo, 1980). This means that pupils' motivation to learn ESL through listening does not only facilitate ESL learning but also prepares them to be marketable in the job market. Scholars like Wolvin and Coakley (1996) suggest that institutions of higher learning should make every effort to expose pupils to listening activities and strategies that prepare them to become good listeners in order to meet employment requirements and become productive employees [3].

Listening is considered to be one of the four macro skills necessary for effective communication in any language according to most researches. As English is universally used as a means of communication, especially on the Internet, English speaking skills should be developed along with the other skills so that these integrated skills will enhance communication competence.

A number of researchers investigated speaking skills of pupils and came to the conclusion about pupils' low level of speaking ability and their inability to speak confidently and fluently. One among the many reasons to take into consideration might be the lack of confidence and anxiety about making errors as stated by Cohen (1988) and in other related studies. Most pupils are not confident in their ability to learn; teachers must overcome their reluctance in order to change this situation.

3 Result

Classroom interaction is also necessary and useful as an educational strategy to enhance listening skills. The role of interaction in a classroom context in enhancing listening skills comes from the understanding of its main types: teacher-learner interaction and learner-learner interaction, where negotiation of meaning and the provision of feedback are highlighted. Classroom interaction involves verbal exchanges between learners and teachers. Teachers should know that the learners need to do most of the talk to activate their listening, since listening skills require practice and exposure.

Some researchers observe that not enough time is given to various exercises and opportunities for the improvement of listening ability. Pupils often complain of ignoring, and discouraging by their teachers for not listening correctly. Although both teachers and pupils are responsible for the poor listening ability of the latter, the teachers, who have the professional knowledge and skills, bear a greater responsibility.

Listening comprehension is a key initial step in communication. The better a student can understand what is being said, the better will be their ability to communicate. In addition, they will be better able to notice the characteristics of the target language which will help improve their language development in all four key skill areas.

Pupils may feel a great deal of pride when they are able to comprehend something in the target language. This can be a great motivating factor in continuing to learn the language, and teachers should do whatever possible to promote this sense of accomplishment. Consequently, teachers need to construct learning activities which will enhance learners' comprehension (listening skills) and motivate them, as well.

The work of Cohen (1988) is a great help in this area. They outline a series of questions which teachers need to consider when preparing listening activities:

- What is the context for listening?
- Should one or two items from the listening exercises be modeled for the whole class so that learners know what to do?
- How many times should the item be heard by pupils?
- How will learners check the accuracy of their listening? (that is, the pupils' answers?)
- Is it possible to check listening accuracy to be done independently or collaboratively?

An effective teacher is aware that pupils are not always able to develop oral comprehension skills on their own; without additional supports listening, by itself, is not enough to develop better listening skills. Here are several activities a teacher can employ to facilitate the development of listening skills.

- Promote active listening: Giving the pupils something to listen for ensures that they are involved in the task. Exercise sheets are another tool that promote active listening;
- Identify listening strategies: Give the pupils tools to guide their listening; such as, looking for specific information, identifying predictable words or phrases, or discussing what they expect in certain forms of speech; such as, newscasts or advertisements.;
- Selecting the most appropriate strategy for presenting the lesson; for example, using a top down (general meaning, summarizing) or bottom up (specific words, word order patterns) approach;
- Allow the pupils to hear as much of the target language as possible while using a variety of teaching methods; for example, sometimes using visual cues, at other times not;
- Use authentic materials; for example, a lecture or a radio announcement in the target language, to help pupils become accustomed to different accents and to a realistic pace of speech;
- Ensure the pupils know the goals of the listening task: is the goal to understand what's being said, to decide whether to keep listening or to obtain specific information?
- Provide opportunities for reflection and discussion so the pupils can share what was heard, what was learned and methods they employed to better understand what was said;
- Organize pre-listening activities, such as providing pupils with relevant vocabulary, reading a related text, looking at a related image or clarifying necessary cultural information etc.;

- Be sure to check level of the listening exercise beforehand to ensure it is an appropriate level for the pupils.

As Gregory L. Rynders, who held a research in developing listening skills in 1999, mentioned, cooperative learning in listening is defined in terms of its purpose for using various learning activities that accommodate pupils' different learning styles to enhance their participation and understanding of the topic by creating an atmosphere of achievement. This is accomplished through cooperative efforts for mutual benefit from each student. It also promotes and enhances pupils' self-worth and communication skills which leads to academic achievement and interpersonal skills.[4]

In developing listening skills, one of the most important aspect is motivation. Listening skills are an essential aspect of the development of motivation which empowers pupils to develop their communication and critical thinking skills necessary for functioning competently in the ESL classroom, the workplace, the home and other places where language learners engage with the public. The development of active listening is essential to pupils' ability to negotiate language outside of the classroom.

Interactive listening skills also improve learners' interpersonal skills, which enable them to establish a healthy relationship with their conversation partners. Despite the necessity of effective listening skills in any form of relationship, it is crucial to note that people can learn how to become good listeners since it is not an innate skill.

The ability to listen well improves in conversation with friends, families, colleagues, teachers and acquaintances. These skills can be developed at home, at school and in the workplace by asking clarifying questions during the whole class discussion at school among others. It is the process that lead to a comprehensive and constructive learning.

In consideration of the above-mentioned data about interactive listening and motivation of ESL pupils' participation in language learning, it is quite clear that interactive listening is imperative in daily life as more time is spent listening to each other in order to respond appropriately in an overall language learning as compared to other learning skills (Morley, 1991).

4 Acknowledgment

In the ESL classroom, it is easy to see that interactive listening plays a significant role in enhancing ESL pupils' comprehensible input and advancement of ESL learning when teachers create lesson plans that encourage pupils to connect the content to their own lives through listening because they are then able to learn on their own. For these reasons, this research contributes to a better understanding of the perceived ESL pupils' motivation and the strategies used by ESL teachers.

Firstly, concerning the promotion of engagement in ESL learning, the study seeks to offer a comprehensive overview of student motivation for learning ESL, which increases when the classroom activities provide them with opportunities for independent or expanded learning outside the classroom with peers or they are related to their future goals outside the classroom. For example, Cohen (1988) stated that "the quality of experience of people who play with and transform the opportunities in their surroundings is clearly more developed as well as more enjoyable". When pupils see connection between classroom activities and real life situations, they are able to expand and enhance their understanding. In other words, the goal is to create active learning experiences and to ensure relevance in the curriculum.

Listening in a LS environment is different from listening in a content class conducted in the mother-tongue and from listening comprehension tasks in the language class. It is very important to teach pupils how to listen. In this light, listening emerges first and foremost as a process and second as a product. Consequently learners become responsible for their own learning and gain control over the listening process. Listening skills can be developed by the instruction of general learning strategies.

Evelyn Pitre (2007) distinguishes three types of listening: content listening, critical listening and emphatic listening. According to his idea, the skills involved in content listening are threefold: identifying the key points; asking clarification questions and verifying content. For critical listening one needs to be able to listen for and test the content; evaluate the logic of the argument, the strength of the evidence, the validity of the conclusions, the implication of the message, the agenda of the speaker, etc. Empathic listening involves the following skills: ability to ask open questions; keep the speaker going; reflect on the content.

Among the basic principles of effective listening, emphasized by Cohen (1988), one could mention the importance of active attention. Listening involves mental activity, including cognitive and affective processing of received information. Consequently, educators enhance listening competence through diligent focus on the mental processes and skills involved in perceptive listening, such as memory, sense making, and evaluation. Listening is a variable communication activity that differs according to the purpose and nature of the listener and the speaker, the content and style of the message, the channel of communication, and the surrounding environment.

Listeners use metacognitive, cognitive, and socio-affective strategies to facilitate comprehension and to make their learning more effective. Metacognitive strategies (e.g. planning, note-taking, transfer, resourcing, self-monitoring, evaluation, selective attention, directed attention and parsing) are important because they oversee, regulate or direct the language learning process. Cognitive strategies (e.g. elaboration, inferencing, imagery, summarization, contextualization, grouping, repetition, problem identification, hypothesis testing, translation and predicting) manipulate the material to be learned or apply a specific technique to a listening task. Socio-affective (e.g. reprise, feedback, uptaking, clarifying, affective control) strategies describe the techniques listeners use to collaborate with others, to verify understanding or to lower anxiety.

As Cohen (1988) notes, one of the difficulties in strategy instruction is the nature of the skill of listening: it is ephemeral and non-visible, which is likely to affect pupils' low assessments of their listening skills and consequently to low motivation and poor success in foreign-language listening comprehension. The results of strategy instruction are controversial, but there is some evidence that consistent, long-term strategy instruction is able to improve learners' strategic activity and lead to better learning outcomes.

Developing good listening skills is an inherent part of the whole learning process. It cannot be taken apart and analyzed as a separate skill without the general context or any other educational methodology. Pupils develop better oral communication skills, they improve listening skills, they also develop reading skills and academic writing, as well as acquire the skills of presentation and develop ability to answer spontaneously to questions. Thus they definitely improve both subject and foreign language competence.

It should be said that listening competence is a complex skill that needs to be developed by practice. Teachers should provide their learners with opportunities to reflect on their listening processes and practices. The role of the teacher is very important, as the teacher not only guides the pupils through the process of listening, but also motivates them and puts them in control of their learning.

The importance of finding effective strategies for teaching listening was demonstrated in research done by Hasan (2000), Kim (2002) and Graham (2003, cited by Vandergrift (2007), who concluded that language learners perceive listening as the most challenging skill to be developed. The grade of difficulty in understanding specific listening input in L2 may generate in learners a feeling of frustration and anxiety.

B)Importance of Developing Listening Skills

Listening is probably the most important skill that people need to develop to acquire a second language since it is the principal means by which learners receive linguistic input. However, it is found that this skill presents the highest level of difficulty in teaching English as a foreign language to elementary grades. Rubin (1994), Dunkel (1991), Rost (1990) and Anderson and Lynch (1988) emphasize that listening skills play a crucial role in communication. Moreover, Oxford (1993) says that "listening is perhaps the most fundamental language skill". Richards (1983) cited by Brown (1994), who mentions a list with some micro skills useful for learners to acquire effective interactive listening strategies. Some of these micro-skills were taken as criteria to develop listening in this project: Retain chunks of language of different length in short- term memory, discriminating among the distinctive sounds of English, recognizing reduced forms of words.[5]

Listening is the process of receiving attending and assigning meaning to aural stimuli. That is, listening is the very first step for us to receive stimuli and then make responses to the external communication can also be regarded as a problem-solving skill, whereas listeners are the problem solvers trying to analyze and decipher a series of signals from the coming message.

It's a highly integrative skill playing an important role in the process of language acquisition and facilitating the emergence of other language skills. Listening, as Cohen (1988) stated, is taking in information from speakers, acknowledging the speakers in a way that invites the communication to continue, providing limited, but encouraging input to the talker's response and carrying the person's ideas one step forward. Furthermore, the phonological system of the reading and writing combined.

Language is acquired by listening and oral communication is impossible without a listening skill that is much more highly developed than the speaking skill serve as the basis for the development of speaking. Additionally, listening involves the interactive process of speaking and listening, and plays a critical role for both an individual to be able to continue the discourse and a medium in the communication process.

It can also stressed that the key to achieving proficiency in speaking is the development of proficiency in listening comprehension. Moreover, Rivers (1984) demonstrated that adults spend 40-50% of communication time listening, 25-30% speaking, 11-16% reading and about 9% writing. In other words, an adult spends more time on listening. However, according to listening in communication than on the other three skills. It's surprising that on the average, people are only about 25 percent effective as listeners. Mueller (1980) indicated that listening is the least understood of the four language skills and consequently the least well taught. Listening is frequently viewed, as it

was claimed, as “an enabling skill, not worthy of attention on its own”. This concept leads people to believe effective listening is instinctive and listeners will automatically understand spoken messages without specific exercises and practice in this skill.

As a result, people make little effort to learn or develop listening skills and unknowingly neglect a vital communication function. In response to the mistaken assumptions, this researcher strongly recommends that the teacher teaches listening comprehension strategies and always integrate listening activities into a language program.

Although the ultimate goal of foreign language pedagogy places stress on the development of four language skills, in comparison with other three language skills, listening has long been the most ignored skill in language teaching. In today’s language classroom, many teachers and learners view speaking as their priority and mistakenly believe that the most useful method to acquire communicative fluency is to increase the opportunity to “talk” rather than to “listen”. The significance and influence of listening have not received priority yet. Reason is individuals’ neglect of the role of the listening skill.

First, some people are convinced that listening skills can be acquired automatically and learned in real-life settings (Braxton, 1999). This mistaken notion, long rooted in people’s mind, reflects the partial reason why language educators and learners don’t regard listening teaching and learning as an important skill in the classroom.

The importance of Extensive Listening is obvious in language learning L2 indicates that a large amount of exposure to input, whether visual or aural, is vital for language acquisition. This suggestion seems to be supported by researchers stressing the importance of quality input in language acquisition.

Cohen (1988) argues that humans acquire listening skills and language by understanding language that contains structures slightly beyond their current level of competence: comprehensible input. He suggests that it is important for the learner to listen to a large amount of spoken English that is relatively easy. Easiness, in his opinion, is another key factor that helps the learner improve listening skills and language. Easiness and interest may be factors that determine whether the learner is actively involved in listening, or not.

Motivation is considered main determinant of second/foreign language (L2) learning achievement. In the last thirty years, there had been considerable amount of research done that explores on the nature and role of motivation in the L2 learning process.

When a student shows little interest in some lecture, this attitude is referred as a lack of motivation. When the problem is seen more deeply, we realize that the student’s lack of motivation is due to several factors. It is now acknowledged that teachers’ teaching style affects to a large extent pupils’ interest and motivation. Although the self-determination theory has concentrated its investigation on children and adolescents, the researcher considers that the support/control is best illustrated at the university level. It seems more reasonable to discuss this issue at the university since pupils who are young adults understand it and respond to it better.

In the investigation of motivation, one often wonders about the role played by such driving force in learning and achievement. It is certainly not always easy to set the effects of motivation on learning. However, most pupils who seem to display a low motivation towards their studies need to be shown how to enjoy their studies more, and mainly how their teachers can enhance their motivation by means of some motivational strategies.

As a matter of fact, people may be motivated towards a certain number of things and may not be motivated towards others. The same person can feel interest in and enjoyment for certain things and at the same time a lack of interest towards others.

Motivation is an important factor in learning a second and foreign language. It is defined as the individual's attitudes, desires, and effort define motivation as concerning energy, direction, persistence and equality-all aspects of activation and intention [6].

Regarding motivation, the main findings of this study indicate that the use of student questions to promote communication from diverse perspectives, taking into consideration student’s interests, teacher’s teaching style are significant motivational tools.

C)Background of extrinsic motivation and instrumental motivation in an ESL classroom

Extrinsic motivation is perceived to attribute to pupils’ educational results under their own control (interested in mastering an ESL topic) while instrumental motivation focuses mainly on the practical and functional use of ESL. Extrinsic motivation and instrumental motivation have been regarded as important factors in ESL achievement because pupils expand their efforts to learn ESL and achieve their goals. For example, international pupils residing in the United States of America may learn English for academic purposes as well as for the purpose of integrating with the people and culture of the country. For that, extrinsic and instrumental motivation are essential for the successful acquisition of ESL. Thus, pupils are motivated because of the exigencies of having to learn a language for a variety of purposes.

ESL information generated both from observations and communications with other pupils. Interactive listeners complete critical thinking activities by clarifying their viewpoints with accurate and rational knowledge to demonstrate their understanding of the topic at hand.

This has direct pedagogical implications. For example, teachers could foster imagination by crafting writing assignments where pupils write about TV shows, movies and discussion questions to stimulate student thought. Also, choosing media with a connection to the unit topic serves as an integral part of the teaching unit, as simulations and games motivate pupils in unique ways. For the purpose of using critical thinking for real-life communication, teachers could establish a classroom environment which provokes pupils' critical thinking and forces them to ask questions about method and evidence (Pearce, Johnson, & Barker, 1995).

For example, pupils should be able to ask "what are the arguments based on?" in order to analyze supporting evidence. This notion of language learning and acquisition could be successful in an intensive oral interaction in ESL when employing questions as a way of presenting and eliciting language. Therefore, interactive listening deals explicitly with ESL acquisition and, implicitly, with ESL learning. This means that pupils need chances to say what they think or feel and to experiment with using language they have heard or seen in a supportive atmosphere, without feeling threatened in order for language learning to take care of itself.

D)ESL Learning Strategies in Listening: According to Cohen, learning strategies refer to pupils' behaviors and techniques they adopt in their effort to learn a second language which is influenced by their motivation, cognitive style, and personality, as well as by specific contexts of use and opportunities for learning.

E)Learner autonomy in Listening: In interactive listening, pupils' motivation increases whenever they are given opportunities to take initiative in their learning which eventually boosts their confidence and abilities to learn ESL more effectively. Therefore, giving pupils opportunities to engage in a class discussion, to ask questions and to constructively argue their viewpoints based on questions raised by classmates becomes beneficial for their vocabulary acquisition [7].

This view suggests that class discussions are crucial resources of ESL learning because they involve listening as well as speaking. Therefore, ESL scholars should be more considerate of the richness of class discussions in their research. This means that ESL teaching and learning ought to be geared towards the development of attentive listening. Pupils need to have varied opportunities in which they could choose the activity that best fits their interests and their style of learning, and increased use of autonomy-supportive behaviors so that all pupils have an opportunity to become involved in a way that is most comfortable for them.

F)Barriers to Effective Listening: Motivation and attitude is the greatest deterrent to effective listening. We hear what we want to hear and we don't hear what we don't want to hear. Without the proper attitude or motivation there is no possible way we will hear, let alone comprehend what the other person is communicating.

As Cohen suggests, many people are ineffective listeners because of a lack of concentration and attention. One of the greatest deterrents to concentration and attention is the mistaken assumption that we can do two things at the same time. The classic example is the person who believes that we can read and listen at the same time. Naturally, nothing is further from the truth. Outside distractions such as phone calls, nearby conversations and people walking by can all easily distract us. It is important to realize that to listen effectively we need to concentrate and ignore distractions. Many people possess negative attitudes toward listening. To them, listening is a passive, compliant act. This is usually considered to be the most obstinate barrier to effective listening. The reason for this is that we are taught to believe that listening is a passive act. Something that other people do, but not ourselves. We believe that talk is power; when we have "the floor" we are in control. Ironically, the reverse is the truth. True power is in listening. When we truly listen to others, they tell us how to best approach them in meeting their needs.

Experience and background have a great bearing on how good a listener we are. As an example, in order to understand speakers with good vocabularies we must also have a similar vocabulary. If we don't, we can either ask the speaker to explain the point or tune them out. Unfortunately, many take the later course.

Where we choose to communicate, that is the listening setting, has a great bearing on how effectively we listen. If we are trying to listen near sources of external distractions, our attention and concentration will be severely challenged. Another ingredient in a positive setting is allowing for an appropriate "personal space". If we are too close to the speaker, it will violate the listener's space. Finally, the environment is important. If it is too hot, cold or another affecting quality, the surroundings will distract from the speakers message. Many ineffective listeners use their emotions to classify or prejudice the speaker. This tends to distort the message positively or negatively. They prejudice the speaker solely on their image. The speaker can be classified as "one of us" or "one of them." Our beliefs and values also determine how well and how objectively we listen to the message content. When we

became too emotionally involved with the content of the message or the speaker, we will systematically distort the message. Day dreaming and fantasizing are perceived by many psychologists and psychiatrists to be a healthy aspect of life. However if we can't control how often and when we do it, it can be extremely detrimental to our listening effectiveness and to our emotional health. As was noted earlier, the reason for daydreaming and fantasizing during the listening process is the fact that people think nearly four times as fast as they can speak. This disparity is used by the skilled listener to their advantage and as an opportunity to let the ineffective listener's mind wander. Certain speakers have a much easier delivery than others. Listeners feel more comfortable when the speakers pace is compatible with theirs. There is a potential for obvious listening problems among people of different delivery styles and listening preferences. A standard response for speaker - listener incompatibility is for the listener to "tune out" the speaker or distort the message. The listener however, can train to increase attention and concentration when confronted with these styles. Finally, Hunsaker and Alessandra suggest that one of the simplest barriers to overcome, but most ignored, is the lack of learned listening skills. Awareness and knowledge of the previously noted barriers as well as the motivation to overcome them. They report that above all, however, the most effective way to overcome the lack of listening skills is to increase motivation to become a better listener [8].

They hypothesize that when people are free to choose to perform an activity, they will seek interesting situations where they can rise to the challenges that the activity presents. By striving to meet these challenges, learners develop a sense of competence in their abilities.

Cohen (1988) says that no single phenomenon reflects the positive potential of human nature as much as extrinsic motivation, which is defined as the inherent tendency to seek out novelty and challenges, to extend and exercise one's capacities, to explore, and to learn. Developmentalists acknowledge that from time of birth, children, in their earliest and healthiest states, are active, inquisitive, curious, and playful, even in the absence of rewards. The whole construct of motivation describes this natural inclination toward assimilation, mastery, spontaneous interest, and exploration that is so essential to cognitive and social development and that represents a principal source of enjoyment throughout life.

Self-determination approach to motivation refers to motivation to perform an activity simply for the pleasure and satisfaction that accompany the action. These feelings of pleasure are derived from fulfilling innate needs for competence and self-determination.

G) Motivation and Learning Strategies: Bacon and Finnemann (1990) investigated the relationship between attitudes, motives, and strategies of university foreign language pupils. The results revealed that motivation played a role in the choice of strategies. Pupils who were not instrumentally motivated used more global/ synthetic strategies, but avoided the use of decoding/analytic comprehension strategies.

Oxford and Ehrman (1995) examined the relationship between language learning strategies and factors such as proficiency, teacher's perception, gender, aptitude, learning style, personality type, ego boundaries, motivation and anxiety. They found a significant correlation between learning strategies and total motivation.

A significant correlation was also found between strategies and intrinsic motivation. The use of metacognitive strategies was positively correlated with intrinsic motivation. Braten and Olaussen investigated the relationship between motivational beliefs and use of learning strategy among Norwegian learners. It was found that when pupils perceive intelligence as a relatively important quality, they tend to use more learning strategies.

Vandergrift (2005) examined the relationships among motivation, metacognition, and proficiency in listening comprehension. Participants were 57 adolescent learners of French who completed two questionnaires. A motivation questionnaire assessed student responses to three orientations related to motivation: intrinsic, and extrinsic. A metacognitive awareness questionnaire assessed the metacognitive strategies used by pupils when listening to authentic texts in French. Most strategies correlated negatively with motivation. A significant correlation was found between intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and use of strategies, but there were more significant relationships between these listening strategies and intrinsic motivation than in the case of extrinsic motivation. Without a doubt, there are still so many things to be done when it comes to conducting research on motivation. In the end, the voluminous amount that might come from studies related to the said topic would further enhance how teachers practice their profession and how pupils acquire and process knowledge in general.[9]

5 Discussion

What is the role of comprehension in developing the listening skills of the pupils? Comprehension plays a great role in raising listening skills of the pupils. It is an invisible power which pushes them to learn more, and it leads to accomplishment of their set goals. While reading feedbacks of the pupils about those conducted 6 lessons, the researcher discovered that there is really huge effect of motivation and it reflected in their opinions. The effect can be seen in the result of this investigation.

How significant is the function of topics to push the pupils to interested in to improve their listening skills? Topics do the function of obtaining positive or negative consequences of targeted learning task. If the topic attracts the attention of the learner, it means that almost 20 % of motivation is given to him/her. It is obvious that a person learns the thing with a great interest if the topic magnetizes the attention of the pupil.

Is there correlation between interested topic and the result in obtaining developed listening skills? Interested topics have influence to develop listening skills of the pupils. If they listen to the tracks, watch videos, listen to the songs or participate in the trainings which are in the theme interesting for them, then the results will be as high as they are expected. All in all, the researcher came to the conclusion that comprehension plays a significant role in developing listening skills of the pupils.

6 Conclusion

The journey of writing and conducting this study has been stimulating, challenging, and most of all very and fulfilling and informative. The researcher identified that the function of comprehension in developing pupils' listening skills is noticeably enormous because this unseen strength pushes them to discover new high peaks of knowledge world. It is recognized by the researcher while conducting the investigation that not only extrinsic motivation guarantees comprehension to have raised skills of the pupils, but also they should have intrinsic type of motivation, strong wish and set goal to enhance on their listening skills. Extrinsic motivation may build the firm foundation to all next processes in comprehension. As far as the researcher is concerned, types of topics and rate of their interesting, average interesting and uninteresting have major influence to attract the attention of the pupils to work on their listening skills. Interest and desire of the pupils towards doing the listening task comes into being automatically if the topic is intriguing, comprehensive and universal. The researcher faced some drawbacks while holding the research:

- There is still an understanding or fear in some pupils' mind that they are not able to develop their listening skills and it is really challenging to motivate them to do this and to persuade them that they can improve it;
- Listening lessons should be paid more attention and it requires more practice;
- Range of topics for Listening lessons should be chosen appropriately according to the interest and level of the pupils.

All points considered, the researcher suggests this study to be used beneficially by teachers or other researchers in the forthcoming future. The researcher has put the aim of continuing investigating this very issue more broadly and completing it perfectly in the next process of her studying.

On the whole, conducting this study was a wonderful, innovative and inspiring experience.

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